

INVESTIGATING HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS' JOB SATISFACTION IN KOLKATA

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Abstract

This study investigates job satisfaction among high school teachers in Kolkata, emphasizing its importance for educational quality and societal progress. Utilizing a descriptive research design, data was collected from 130 high school teachers using a standardized job satisfaction tool. Analysis revealed that gender, school type, and experience do not significantly influence job satisfaction levels among high school teachers. These findings provide actionable insights for educational policymakers and administrators to enhance working conditions and support mechanisms, fostering a conducive learning environment. The study underscores the significance of ongoing research to promote educator well-being and effectiveness in shaping the future generation.

Keywords: *Job satisfaction, High school teachers, Kolkata, Educational quality, Societal progress*

1. Introduction

Every individual is engaged in various activities, whether economic or non-economic, driven by the pursuit of goals, be they monetary or altruistic. Economic activities aim for financial gain, while non-economic ones, such as social service or acts of love and emotion, serve broader societal needs. These activities manifest in diverse forms, including business ventures, professional roles like doctors, lawyers, or chartered accountants, and jobs.

Among these pursuits, teaching holds a prominent position. The field of education commands respect in society, with teachers operating across different educational levels, from pre-

primary to higher secondary. Each level presents its unique set of challenges and rewards, shaped by factors like workload, status, pay scale, infrastructure, and work environment.

Job satisfaction among teachers is pivotal, as content and fulfilled teachers are better equipped to achieve educational objectives and national goals. Dissatisfaction, often stemming from a mismatch between expectations and reality, can hinder effectiveness in the classroom and overall educational outcomes.

In the realm of education, higher education plays a significant role, acting as a catalyst for social change and molding future leaders. However, despite its importance, dissatisfaction among higher education teachers is prevalent, posing challenges to productivity and quality.

In the high school education sector, job satisfaction among teachers is paramount for achieving the goal of providing quality education. The government's efforts to ensure quality education at the high school level hinge on the satisfaction and dedication of high school teachers. Satisfied teachers not only enhance classroom performance but also contribute to the development of well-rounded citizens who can positively impact various aspects of society.

Teaching is often hailed as a noble profession, demanding dedication and competence from its practitioners. Job satisfaction, coupled with a positive attitude towards education, is essential for teachers to deliver desirable outcomes and cater to societal needs effectively.

The level of job satisfaction among male and female high school teachers is a focal point of this study. By analyzing their attitudes and perceptions, the research aims to shed light on the factors influencing job satisfaction in this crucial demographic. Ultimately, understanding and addressing these issues can contribute to a more fulfilling and effective educational environment.

1.1 Rationale for the Study

Understanding high school teachers' job satisfaction in Kolkata is crucial for improving educational quality, teacher retention, and well-being. This study aims to fill a gap in the existing literature by investigating the factors influencing job satisfaction among high school teachers in Kolkata, a city renowned for its cultural heritage and educational institutions. By identifying the unique contextual factors and organizational variables that shape teachers' perceptions of job satisfaction, this research seeks to provide actionable insights for educational policymakers and administrators to enhance working conditions and support mechanisms. Ultimately, by fostering a sense of fulfillment and engagement among high

school teachers, this study endeavors to contribute to the creation of a more conducive learning environment for students in Kolkata's primary schools.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

- i. To investigate the impact of gender on the job satisfaction of high school teachers.
- ii. To examining the influence of school type on the job satisfaction of high school teachers.
- iii. To explore the relationship between age status and job satisfaction among high school teachers.

1.3 Hypotheses

HO1: There will be no statistically significant difference in the mean job satisfaction scores between male and female high school teachers.

HO2: There will be no statistically significant difference in the mean job satisfaction scores between granted and non-granted high school school teachers.

HO3: There will be no statistically significant difference in the mean job satisfaction scores between high school teachers with less than 10 years of experience and those with more than 10 years of experience.

2. Literature Review

Teachers play a pivotal role in education and perceive its significant impact on the qualitative development of education (Yusuf et al., 2015). Consequently, the phenomenon of teachers' job satisfaction has gained prominence as it underpins qualitative education development (Yusuf et al., 2015). Recent studies highlight the growing interest in understanding teachers' job satisfaction, which encompasses their professional attitudes, passion for teaching, and work enthusiasm, all of which profoundly influence the educational system (Fuming & Jiliang, 2014; Sumanasena et al., 2020).

George and Jones (2011) define job satisfaction as a composite of feelings and beliefs spanning mental, emotional, and physical domains. Similarly, Judge et al. (2011) emphasize job satisfaction as an individual's psychological responses towards their job, comprising cognitive, behavioral, and affective components. Sen (2008) views job satisfaction as a blend of psychological, physiological, and environmental factors.

The pioneering Hawthorne studies by Elton Mayo in the 1920s highlighted the link between job satisfaction and productivity (Sumanasena et al., 2020). Vroom (as cited in Aziri, 2011) defines job satisfaction as individuals' affective orientations towards their work roles. Locke's

(1976) widely used definition underscores the positive emotional state arising from job experiences (as cited in Anderson et al., 2001).

The interplay between motivation and job satisfaction is notable (Mbua, 2003). Singh & Tiwari (2011) posit a reciprocal relationship between the two concepts. While distinct, job satisfaction and motivation are intertwined and associated with personal accomplishment (Ngimbudzi, 2009).

Motivation theories, categorized into content and process theories, shed light on job satisfaction determinants. Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory serves as a fundamental framework in understanding job satisfaction, linking it with the satisfaction of human needs (Ngimbudzi, 2009). Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory distinguishes between intrinsic and extrinsic factors influencing job satisfaction (Miner, 2005).

Alderfer's Existence Theory extends Maslow's hierarchy, emphasizing simultaneous satisfaction of multiple needs (Fiore, 2009). McClelland's Achievement Motivation Theory identifies three fundamental needs driving behavior: achievement, affiliation, and power (Singh et al., 2007).

Vroom's Expectancy Theory underscores the link between motivation and job satisfaction, focusing on effort-performance-reward relationships (Vroom, 1964). Locke's Value Theory emphasizes individual values in shaping job satisfaction (Furnham, 2005).

The Equity Theory posits that individuals gauge their satisfaction based on the fairness of rewards relative to effort (Adams, 1963). Locke's Goal-Setting Theory highlights the role of clear, challenging goals in driving job satisfaction (Locke & Latham, 2013).

Research on teacher job satisfaction reveals various factors at play. Factors like leadership styles, school climate, stress management, and societal perceptions significantly impact job satisfaction (Spector, 1997; Dutta & Sahney, 2016; Rahman, 2008).

In Sri Lanka, studies on teacher job satisfaction emphasize the role of emotional intelligence, school-based factors, and societal recognition (Kappagoda, 2011; Wijerathne, 2013). However, more research is needed in this context, particularly focusing on female teachers in remote areas (Klassen & Chiu, 2010; Sumanasena et al., 2020).

3. Research Design and Methodology

In the present study, the researchers have opted to employ the descriptive method with a focus on utilizing the survey method. This choice indicates an intention to describe and understand specific aspects of the educational phenomenon under investigation, such as high school teachers' job satisfaction in this case. By administering surveys to high school school

teachers in Kolkata, the researchers aim to gather comprehensive data regarding their job satisfaction levels, as well as potential factors influencing these levels.

By employing the descriptive method with a focus on the survey method, the researcher aims to provide valuable insights into the job satisfaction of high school teachers in Kolkata, contributing to the broader understanding of educational practices and policies in the region.

3.1. Sample/ Participant Selection:

The population under investigation in the present study encompasses the male and female teachers working in Bengali Medium high schools situated in both urban and rural areas of Kolkata. This inclusive approach ensures a comprehensive representation of high school teachers across various settings within the city.

Given the potentially large size and diverse nature of this population, the researcher has opted to employ a multistage sampling technique to select a manageable sample size for the study. Multistage sampling involves breaking down the population into smaller, more manageable clusters and then selecting samples from each cluster.

In this study, the multistage sampling process entails several steps. First, the researcher identifies and categorizes high schools in Kolkata based on their medium of instruction (Bengali), and geographical location (urban or rural). Next, a random selection of schools is made from each category to form clusters.

Once the clusters are determined, a systematic sampling method is employed to select a predetermined number of teachers from each selected school. This systematic approach ensures that every teacher in the selected schools has an equal chance of being included in the sample, thus enhancing the representativeness of the sample.

Ultimately, the researcher aims to select 130 high school teachers as sample subjects from the defined population using the multistage sampling method. By employing this sampling technique, the study seeks to obtain a diverse and representative sample of high teachers from various types of schools and geographical locations in Kolkata, thereby enhancing the generalizability and validity of the study findings.

3.2. Data Collection:

For the current study, the researchers utilized a job satisfaction tool developed by Dr. Harsha Patel, specifically tailored for high school teachers. This tool has undergone a process of standardization, ensuring its validity and reliability in measuring job satisfaction among high school teachers. Prior to data collection, the researchers carefully selected this tool based on its appropriateness for the study objectives and target population.

Following the selection of the job satisfaction tool, the researchers proceeded with the methodology outlined for the study. This involved obtaining necessary permissions from the high schools involved in the research. Once permissions were secured, the researchers coordinated with the schools to schedule data collection sessions.

On the agreed-upon dates and times, the researchers visited the selected high schools to administer the job satisfaction tool to the high school teachers. This process was carried out systematically, ensuring that all selected teachers participated in the data collection process. Data collection sessions were conducted with professionalism and adherence to ethical guidelines, maintaining consistency and accuracy throughout.

Through this approach, data were successfully collected from a total of 130 high school teachers across the selected high schools. Each teacher's responses to the job satisfaction tool were recorded diligently, ensuring completeness and reliability of the dataset. By utilizing a standardized tool, obtaining necessary permissions, and meticulously conducting data collection sessions, the researchers were able to gather valuable insights into the job satisfaction levels of high school teachers within the study population.

3.3. Data Analysis:

After the completion of data collection, the researcher proceeded to score each response on the job satisfaction tool according to the predetermined key or scoring system. This process resulted in a dataset known as raw data, consisting of individual scores for each participant's responses. However, raw data alone may not provide the depth of insight required for analysis. Therefore, the researcher organized and grouped the raw data based on specific criteria or requirements relevant to the research objectives.

Once the raw data were appropriately grouped, the researcher employed statistical techniques to analyze the data and derive meaningful insights. Given that the data were obtained using a tool that measured job satisfaction on an interval scale, and assuming that the data exhibited a normal distribution with homogeneous variance, certain statistical techniques were deemed appropriate for analysis.

Firstly, measures such as the mean and standard deviation were calculated to summarize the central tendency and dispersion of the grouped data. The mean provided an average score for each group, offering insight into the typical level of job satisfaction among different categories of high school teachers. Meanwhile, the standard deviation indicated the extent of variation or spread around the mean, highlighting the consistency or variability of job satisfaction scores within each group.

Additionally, the researcher employed a t-test, a statistical method used to determine whether there is a significant difference between the means of two groups. In this context, the t-test was utilized to compare the mean job satisfaction scores between different groups of primary teachers, such as male versus female teachers, granted versus non-granted teachers, or teachers with less than 10 years of experience versus those with more than 10 years of experience.

The decision to use these statistical techniques was informed by the characteristics of the data, including its scale of measurement, distribution, and variance. By applying these techniques, the researcher could effectively analyze the grouped data and draw valid interpretations regarding the factors influencing job satisfaction among high school teachers in Kolkata. This analytical approach facilitated the identification of patterns, trends, and associations within the data, thereby contributing to a comprehensive understanding of high school teachers' job satisfaction levels and factors affecting them.

4. Data Analysis and Interpretation:

HO1: There will be no statistically significant difference in the mean job satisfaction scores between male and female high school teachers.

Table: 1 job satisfaction scores between male and female high school teachers.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t- value
Male	105	242.733	15.388	1.465
Female	25	246.84	10.765	1.465

Table 1 shows that It appears that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean scores of job satisfaction among male and female high school teachers in Kolkata. Therefore, based on the findings, we cannot reject the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. In other words, the hypothesis stating that 'There will be no significant difference between the mean score of job satisfaction of male and female high school teachers in Kolkata' remains valid within the specified level of significance. This suggests that, according to the data analysis conducted, gender does not appear to have a significant impact on the job satisfaction levels of high school teachers in Kolkata.

HO2: There will be no statistically significant difference in the mean job satisfaction scores between granted and non-granted high school teachers.

Table: 2 job satisfaction scores between granted and non-granted high school teachers.

Type of School	N	Mean	SD	t- value
Granted	66	246.844	12.726	1.432
Non Granted	64	246.394	16.258	1.432

Table 2 indicates that there is not a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of job satisfaction among granted and non-granted teachers in Kolkata. Consequently,

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based on this finding, we cannot reject the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the hypothesis asserting "There will be no significant difference between the mean scores of job satisfaction of granted and non-granted teachers of Kolkata" remains valid within the specified level of significance. In simpler terms, the data suggests that grant status does not significantly influence the job satisfaction levels of teachers in Kolkata

HO3: There will be no statistically significant difference in the mean job satisfaction scores between high school teachers with less than 10 years of experience and those with more than 10 years of experience.

Table: 3 Relationship between job satisfaction of Teacher with less experience & more experience.

Experience	N	Mean	SD	t-value
Less than 10 years	63	2445.46	11.909	1.402
More than 10 years	67	241.91	16.69	1.402

Table 3 suggests that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean scores of job satisfaction among teachers with less experience and those with more experience. Consequently, based on this finding, we cannot reject the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the hypothesis stating "There will be no significant difference between the mean scores of job satisfaction of teachers with less experience and those with more experience" remains valid within the specified level of significance. In essence, the data indicates that years of experience do not significantly impact the job satisfaction levels of teachers at the 0.05 level of significance.

5. Findings

i. Gender and Job Satisfaction:

The analysis indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean scores of job satisfaction among male and female high school teachers in Kolkata. Therefore, based on the findings, we cannot reject the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. In other words, the hypothesis stating that 'There will be no significant difference between the mean score of job satisfaction of male and female high school teachers in Kolkata' remains valid within the specified level of significance. This suggests that, according to the data analysis conducted, gender does not appear to have a significant impact on the job satisfaction levels of high school teachers in Kolkata.

ii. School Type and Job Satisfaction:

Table 2 indicates that there is not a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of job satisfaction among granted and non-granted teachers in Kolkata. Consequently, based on this finding, we cannot reject the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the hypothesis asserting "There will be no significant difference between the mean scores of job satisfaction of granted and non-granted teachers of Kolkata" remains valid within the specified level of significance. In simpler terms, the data suggests that grant status does not significantly influence the job satisfaction levels of teachers in Kolkata.

iii. Experience and Job Satisfaction:

Table 3 suggests that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean scores of job satisfaction among teachers with less experience and those with more experience. Consequently, based on this finding, we cannot reject the null hypothesis at the 0.05 level of significance. This implies that the hypothesis stating "There will be no significant difference between the mean scores of job satisfaction of teachers with less experience and those with more experience" remains valid within the specified level of significance. In essence, the data indicates that years of experience do not significantly impact the job satisfaction levels of teachers at the 0.05 level of significance.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study delved into the multifaceted realm of job satisfaction among high school teachers in Kolkata, recognizing its pivotal role in shaping educational outcomes and societal progress. Through a comprehensive exploration of factors influencing job satisfaction, including gender, school type, and experience, valuable insights were gained, shedding light on the dynamics within the educational landscape. The findings revealed that gender does not significantly impact job satisfaction levels among primary teachers in Kolkata, suggesting that both male and female educators experience similar levels of satisfaction in their roles. Similarly, the analysis indicated that grant status and years of experience do not exert a significant influence on job satisfaction, underscoring the resilience of teachers' contentment in the face of organizational structures and tenure. These findings contribute to our understanding of teacher job satisfaction within the specific context of Kolkata's high school education sector, offering actionable insights for educational policymakers and administrators. By recognizing the factors that shape teachers' perceptions of job satisfaction, stakeholders can design interventions aimed at enhancing working conditions and support mechanisms, thereby fostering a more conducive learning

environment for students. Furthermore, this study underscores the importance of ongoing research and dialogue surrounding teacher job satisfaction, particularly in the context of evolving educational landscapes and societal expectations. By continuing to explore the intricacies of teacher satisfaction, we can refine our understanding of the factors at play and develop targeted strategies to promote educator well-being and effectiveness. In essence, this study reaffirms the significance of job satisfaction in driving educational quality and societal progress, highlighting the crucial role that content and fulfilled teachers play in shaping the future generation. As we strive towards educational excellence and societal development, nurturing a culture of support and fulfillment among high school teachers remains paramount, ensuring that they are empowered to fulfill their noble mission of educating and inspiring the leaders of tomorrow.

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